

Educational Cooperation between Uzbekistan and Germany

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Abstract. *This article is analyzed considering cooperation between Uzbekistan and Germany in the field of Education. In may 2023, details of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's visit to Germany were reported. In addition, in this article we will talk about what educational relations are between Germany and Uzbekistan and the great interest in the study of German culture and language in Uzbekistan, as well as the establishment of partnerships with more than 30 German universities in the field of higher education at the moment.*

Keywords: *Germany, Uzbekistan, educational relations, DAAD, VET, "all this is a family!"*.

Introduction

In recent years, the cooperation of Uzbekistan and Germany has been developing consistently. Cooperation between our countries has a multifaceted nature, covering the trade and economic, investment and technological sectors. Effective cooperation has been made in areas such as security, human rights protection, Environmental Protection, science and education, expansion of cultural ties and Exchange in tourism. Over the years, Germany has supported various educational projects in Uzbekistan, including providing training and advice for vocational training institutions and supporting the development of the German language in Uzbekistan. In recent years, there has also been an increase in the establishment of German language courses and language centers in Uzbekistan. In addition, many bilateral treaties on education and culture have been signed between the two countries, establishing cooperation and exchange between universities, scientific institutions and educational organizations in Germany and Uzbekistan.

In general, educational ties between Germany and Uzbekistan have become strong and developing, with both sides recognizing the importance of educational and cultural exchange in strengthening relations between the two states. Further details regarding the educational relationship between Germany and Uzbekistan: in 1994-2014, Germany, through its Academic Exchange Service (DAAD), allocated about 4,700 scholarships to Uzbek students to study at German universities. In 1995, with the support of Germany, The Tashkent International School was established, providing education to students of various nationalities in Uzbekistan, including German language courses. In 2008, the German - Uzbek University was founded in Tashkent, which offers programs in engineering, economics and linguistics, etc. In 2012, the Uzbek - German Forum on human rights was established, aimed at promoting human rights and democracy in Uzbekistan through educational and cultural initiatives.

The German government also funded various educational projects in Uzbekistan, such as the construction of new schools and the development of educational materials. In recent years, the focus on vocational education and vocational training (VET) has been increasing in relations between Germany and Uzbekistan, while German organizations such as the Chamber of Commerce of Germany in Uzbekistan provide training and advice for vocational training institutions in Uzbekistan. Education relations between Germany and Uzbekistan are characterized by cooperation and mutual

assistance in areas such as academic exchange, language education and vocational education. LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METADAGOGY Minister of Higher Education, Science and innovation Ibrahim Abdurahmonov was in the Federal Republic of Germany as part of a delegation led by the Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan, held a number of meetings as part of the visit and reached a number of agreements for the development of bilateral cooperation. In particular, a meeting was held with Secretary of State Thomas Rachel of the German Federal Ministry of Education and research (BMBF). The meeting discussed the work carried out in cooperation and plans for the future. As a result of the meeting, the parties agreed to organize a joint competition of scientific projects in order to promote dialogue between Uzbek–German scientists and to attract financial funds for this purpose. Organization of scientific internship programs for young scientists from Uzbekistan. In cooperation with the BMBF, it was discussed that the qualification of scientists and researchers of our country will be increased in advanced German scientific institutions and laboratories. Negotiations were also conducted with the German society for international cooperation (GIZ) to "support the processes of reform and modernization of the vocational education system in Uzbekistan" and "professional education for economic growth sectors in Central Asia". In addition, in the field of professional education, with the support of the German bank KfW, it was agreed to support the project "improvement of the Professional education system". In 2019, the German-Uzbek Institute of Applied Research (GUIAR) was established at the Tashkent State Technical University on the basis of funding from the German Federal Ministry of Education and research. The institute aims to develop applied research in areas such as renewable energy, water resources management and civil engineering. In 2020, the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD) launched a new program called "University - business cooperation", aimed at promoting cooperation between Uzbek universities and German companies in areas such as engineering, informatics and Natural Sciences. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the German government provided financial assistance to Uzbekistan to purchase equipment for the implementation of distance education initiatives. This assistance included providing Uzbek students and teachers with laptops and tablets. In May 2021, Germany and Uzbekistan signed a "joint declaration on cooperation in Higher Education". The declaration aims to further strengthen educational ties between the two states, promote academic exchange, support joint research projects, and expand vocational education and training initiatives. Educational ties between Germany and Uzbekistan continue to develop and expand, with an increased focus on Applied Research, strengthening cooperation between universities and business, and supporting distance education initiatives after the pandemic.

The Goethe Institute collaborates with the German study hall in Tashkent with two libraries in Andijan and Urgench. Readers located in all regions of the country on this network have the opportunity to directly use German-owned news media. The main topics are: topics related to belletristics and local lore, and for teachers and students in other countries, such as teaching German as a foreign language, pedagogy and forms of Education. Collaborative libraries and study halls are included in the system of libraries in receiving states. Thus, partner libraries provide library facilities and dedicated infrastructure. The Goethe Institute provides educational and informational materials to partner libraries annually. On April 14-15, 2022, PASCH School No. 19 with German A1+ and B1 students visited the exhibition "all this family" at the Goethe Institute's partner library in Urgench. An exhibit was presented to the streamers, who, after a brief excursion with information on the subject, said "it's all family!" as part of the exhibition, interesting master classes began. Especially interesting was the last assignment, which was completed by dividing groups, in which students had to choose a book within 10 minutes, perform roles on a small topic based on their choices. After that, for another 10 minutes, the roles were divided and the games were shown. At the end of the master classes, the exhibition was shot with 10-minute questions and answers to whom and why it was intended in the first place, its benefits, what books in particular to the audience are where you can turn. As well as reading German language literature, the streamers debated many interesting topics such as the concept of family, parent-child relationships, upbringing. Organized master classes within the framework of the Korgazma made a great impression on the streamers. Organized by the Munich International Youth Library and The Tashkent Goethe Institute, this exhibition will allow you to come to our partner library and read books with your family until mid-May.

Discussion

One of the global and priority principles of social development is the process of integration, which is manifested at all stages of human activity, including in the fields of Science and education. Cooperation between Uzbekistan and Germany in the field of Science and education has a long history. In particular, German scientists, representatives of the scientific circle have long been very interested in the history, national traditions and traditions of our country. In turn, the general public of our country also attached special importance to the study of Germany's past and the path of modern development, socio-economic image. In this regard, it is worth remembering that the term "Central Asia" was first used by the famous German scientist Alexander von Humboldt in his three-volume work "research of the Central Asian mountain ranges and comparison of climates", published in Paris in 1843. In it, the scientist describes Central Asia as a separate, specific region, based on the study of the internal irrigation system and mountain ranges. After that, the concept of "Central Asia" has remained in use to this day as a geographical term. Currently, Germany is known as a state with a broad emphasis on educational and professional orientation, science and scientific research. This is also confirmed by the fact that 91 Nobel laureates are representatives of this state. Today it can be explained by the fact that more than 800 students and scientific researchers of our country are studying in German higher education institutions. Having studied advanced foreign experience and aimed at introducing modern technologies in Uzbekistan in various fields, such opportunities for young people are being created in cooperation with the relevant ministries and departments of our country by the organizations of the German Academic Exchange Service, the Goethe Institute in Tashkent, the Konrad Adenauer and Friedrich Ebert foundations in our country, the Institute for International Cooperation.

In the following years, the high attention paid to the field of education and science, including the favorable conditions created for young people to gain knowledge on the basis of international standards, the scale of work carried out to support research projects, are of great interest in Germany. It serves to develop the cooperation of our countries in the cultural and humanitarian sphere at a new stage. The relationship between Germany and Uzbekistan in the field of Education has undergone significant changes over the past few decades, and some of the differences between these relations can be summarized as follows:

1. In the early years of Uzbekistan's independence, Germany's participation in education was limited to providing humanitarian assistance and technical assistance. Over time, this support expanded to include a number of educational programs, including academic exchange and vocational training.
2. As German cooperation with Uzbekistan deepened, the focus shifted from aid programs to long-term cooperation. These collaborations have led to many collaborations between universities, researchers and students from both countries, opening up new opportunities for academic advancement and cultural exchange.
3. Germany's role in Uzbekistan's education has evolved from being primarily focused on higher education into the field of professional education and Language Teaching. This expansion allowed more Uzbeks to acquire practical skills, increase language skills, and increase employment opportunities.
4. Another notable difference in education relations between Germany and Uzbekistan over the past years has been the active participation of the private sector. German companies have established professional education programs in Uzbekistan, developed a skilled workforce and increased the country's competitiveness in world markets. Educational ties between Germany and Uzbekistan have evolved from a focus mainly on basic humanitarian aid and technical assistance to a more significant and meaningful long-term cooperation covering a variety of fields. On April 27, 2023, at the initiative of the representative office of the German economy in Central Asia, a delegation made up of German universities and government agencies visited the Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent. The event was attended by representatives of 6 German universities, the Thuringian state office, the delegation of the German economy, led by the Thuringian Secretary of state for Economics, higher education

and digital affairs. As part of the visit, the members of the delegation got acquainted with the Technopark, laboratory and startup projects of the University of Turin in Tashkent. At the meeting, TTPU and German universities, exchanged information about their activities. They discussed the following areas in order to further expand cooperation.

In particular: Signing a memorandum of understanding on cooperation between the Polytechnic University of Turin and German universities;

- Organization of internship programs in German industrial enterprises for TTPU students;
- Establishment of Summer Schools (summer school) in both universities; * Cooperation with Erasmus + projects (Erasmus + inter-institutional agreement signing); * sharing library resources and online use of electronic resources for the use of educational and scientific databases;
- International mobility: exchange of students and doctoral students, researchers and teachers funded by Erasmus+ programs;
- International cooperation in the field of teaching: creation of joint programs in undergraduate, graduate and doctoral programs. At the end of the meeting, a memorandum of understanding and an agreement on the exchange of students was signed with the Nordhausen University of Applied Sciences. Great interest in cooperation was also expressed by the rest of the universities and it was agreed to sign a memorandum of cooperation in the future.

In May 2023, as part of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's visit to Germany, the head of state, together with a German colleague, participated in the opening of the exhibition "archaeological treasures of Uzbekistan – from Alexander Makedonsky to the Kushans", organized at the James Simon Gallery in Berlin. The exhibition will last until January 14, 2024, and during its activities, various cultural events are held that introduce the German public and guests of the country to the rich history, unique culture and traditions of the Uzbek people. The exhibition displays 285 historical items from the collection of 9 museums in Uzbekistan.

In turn, Uzbekistan also has a growing interest in Germany, its culture, language, education and business opportunities.

Today, nearly 300,000 schoolchildren in Uzbekistan study Goethe, Schiller and Kant. 24 schools are teaching German in a deepened way. 6 of them, namely schools in Tashkent, Samarkand, Marghilon, Fergana, Andijan and Bukhara, have the right to issue a German language diploma. There are also more than 4,000 Uzbek graduate students and doctoral students studying at various universities in Germany.

Currently, the Goethe Institute, the Institute of international cooperation of the Association of German people's universities, the representative office of the Central Directorate of schools abroad are successfully operating in Uzbekistan. Along with them in our country K.Adenauer and F.Representative offices of Ebert funds are opened, which promote the implementation of projects in the socio-economic sphere.

Within the framework of interregional cooperation, fraternal relations have been established between Tashkent and the cities of Berlin, Bukhara and Bonn. Effective cultural and educational exchanges, sustainable development projects are being implemented.

Today, about 5,000 residents of ethnic German nationality live in Uzbekistan. All conditions for preserving their national traditions and culture have been created for them. In our country, citizens of German nationality are seen not only as an integral part of Uzbek society, but also as a bridge connecting the two states.

Conclusion

In recent years, the cooperation of Uzbekistan and Germany has been successfully developing in political, trade-economic, cultural-educational, humanitarian directions. In particular, the partnership in science and education between the two countries has a long history. German scientists,

representatives of the scientific circle have long been seriously interested in the history, national traditions and traditions of our country. In turn, the general public of our country also attached special importance to the study of Germany's past and the path of modern development, socio-economic image.

Currently, the support of initiatives for the training of qualified specialists is an important aspect of the multifaceted Uzbekistan-Germany relationship. The opening of the representative office of the federal land authorities of Saxony at the University of geological sciences can be assessed as a continuation of the same process.

In connection with this event, the heads of various ministries and departments, professors and teachers of higher educational institutions, the Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of Germany to Uzbekistan Dr. Tilo Klinner, the Minister of Science, Culture and tourism of the Federal Land of Saxony Sebastian Gemkov took part in the event.

It was noted that at the last time, the high attention paid to the field of education and science in our country, including the favorable conditions created for young people to gain knowledge on the basis of international norms, the work carried out to support research projects, are of interest in Germany. In general, the overall efforts today serve to take the cooperation of our states in the cultural and humanitarian sphere to a new level.

The purpose of opening this representative office is to cooperate in the training of specialists for the fields of mining, geology, Mechanical Engineering, Materials Science, geoecology, economics and Business Administration and to expand the exchange of students. It is also planned to organize preparatory courses in Uzbekistan to improve the professional training of young people who intend to study in Saxony.

On May 3, 2023, the Bellevue Palace in Berlin hosted talks between President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev and President of the Federal Republic of Germany Frank-Walter Steinmeier.

An agreement was reached on the preparation of a comprehensive program for the study of the German language in Uzbekistan, including the expansion of the activities of the Goethe Institute in the regions of our country.

Education systems have been created in both Germany and Uzbekistan that prioritize the development of human capital through primary, secondary and higher education. Germany is known for its strong vocational education and education system, while Uzbekistan has seen a strong emphasis on STEM education in recent years. In addition, both nations have attempted to develop their education system internationally through exchange programs, joint research projects, and collaboration between universities. This provided opportunities for students from both nations to interact with different cultures and gain valuable international experience. In terms of difficulties, both Germany and Uzbekistan faced problems related to inequality in education, in particular, the possibility of education of the disadvantaged population. Both nations have difficulty adapting their education systems to the demands of the rapidly changing world economy. In general, the relations between Germany and Uzbekistan in the field of education are positive, indicating that both countries are in favor of developing a strong educational system and developing international cooperation in the field of Education. While some challenges, such as inequality in education and adaptation to changing economic conditions, have to be overcome, efforts by both states offer a general idea of the importance of education in shaping the future of their societies. Through constant cooperation and dialogue, there are great opportunities for the relationship in this sector to develop in the coming years and benefit both countries.

The visit of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Federal Republic of Germany in January 2019 and the visit of German federal President Frank-Walter Steinmeier to Uzbekistan in may 2019 brought bilateral political, trade-economic and Humanitarian-Cultural Relations to a new level.

Uzbekistan has a great interest in learning German culture and language. German is the second most widely spoken foreign language in the Republic. At present, in the field of higher education, partnerships have been established with more than 30 higher educational institutions in Germany, and the exchange of students, specialists and pedagogical personnel has been established. Cooperation relations between Tashkent and Berlin, Samarkand and the cities of Bremen, Bukhara and Bonn play an important role in the development of bilateral cultural and humanitarian relations.

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